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GRANT AGREEMENT NUMBER 957781

WP2– Foundations

D2.5 – Report on cybersecurity framework design & specifications for data protection & privacy v1

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Table of Abbreviations and Acronyms

COMSEC	COMmunication SECurity
DER	Distributed Energy Resources
DPIA	Data Privacy Impact Assessment
DR	Demand Response
DSO	Distribution System Operator
EMSEC	EMmision SECurity
EU	European Union
FHE	Fully Homomorphic Encryption
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
LEC	Local Energy Community
LWE	Learning With Errors
RWLE	Ring Learning With Errors
SEAC	SEcurity Access Control
SHE	Somewhat Homomorphic Encryption
SIMD	Single Instruction Multiple Data
TC	Threat Category
TLS	Transport Layer Security
TRANSEC	TRANsmision SECurity
UC	Use Case
VPN	Virtual Private Network

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable discusses the security mechanisms that are going to be implemented to the ACCEPT solution, in order to mitigate threats that may be present in the data communication procedures. As the whole ACCEPT architecture should respect the General Data Protection Regulation, a lot of attention has been given to the definition of the needs for such purposes, and the presentation of a Homomorphic encryption solution serving as an anonymization technique. Additionally, there is a thorough presentation of a RISK assessment that is going to be conducted for all pilot sites, in a form of a questionnaire.

Task T2.4-Security Access Control (SEAC) framework design & guidelines for technical solution developers is part of WP2 – Foundations. The aim of the WP2 is to thoroughly analyse the end-user requirements of both energy consumers/ prosumers as well as energy communities and other market actors that will operate as retailers, aggregators or Energy Service Companies in line with Task T3.1- ACCEPT Living Labs design & establishment activities, part of WP3-Energy Governance, communities and demonstration site analysis. All analysis and mechanism presented in this deliverable are in a form of Security Guidelines as the development of the ACCEPT infrastructure is still under development. More technical details on the implementations will be given in the Deliverable D2.6-Report on cybersecurity framework design & specifications for data protection & privacy v2.

1. Introduction

1.1. Scope of the Deliverable

In the context of **Task T2.4-Security Access Control (SEAC) framework design & guidelines for technical solution developers** of **WP2 – Foundations**, the security risks that may occur as well as the data handling processes, in any use case tested, will be analysed and evaluated. The analysis and evaluation will be based on the current General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) of the EU (European Union). The purpose of the task is to identify and mitigate any security or privacy threat that may be brought up in the project. The overall security framework that will be implemented aims to minimize any risks related to private data misuse. The framework focuses on protecting the two major aspects, the anonymization of the collected data from the end-user and the security of the exchanged-over-the-network information. The assessment of security and privacy threats is presented separately for every use case tested and for every stakeholder affected. In Table 1 below, the objectives of the versions of this deliverable are outlined.

Table 1. Deliverable Objectives.

Deliverable	Objectives
D2.5 – Report on cybersecurity framework design & Specifications for data protection & privacy v1	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Outline the cybersecurity framework with respect to data management plan 2. Outline the methodology to identify security hazards and privacy risks per use case and per stakeholder affected. 3. Specifications under a robust design of security, followed during the ACCEPT development activities
D2.6 – Report on cybersecurity framework design & Specifications for data protection & privacy v2	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Continuous assessment of the outlined methodology for identifying security hazards and privacy risks. 2. Fine-tuning of the proposed framework during the development activities. 3. Final version Report on the final cybersecurity framework,

1.2. Interdependencies with other tasks and deliverables

Being part of Work Package 2, WP2 – foundations, T2.4 and deliverable D2.5 and its updated version D2.6 draw close ties with the activities of other tasks of the same WP, and their respective deliverables. Such as T2.1 – Market actor & Prosumer requirement & Business scenario definition, and deliverable D2.1 – Business scenarios, use cases & requirements, where the use cases examined are analyzed and T2.3 – System architecture design, configuration & elaboration, and deliverable D2.3 – system architecture description v1 (due in M10), where the system architecture is described. Security mechanisms are a crucial part of the overall system design, as they are developed in order to protect the system of malicious attacks and to offer users a safe experience, keeping the functionality of the services high. The overall security design is directly connected with the system architecture. The results produced of this deliverable act as an input for the Task T4.1-Smart Home IoT solution definition & Building Information Management Layer configuration, as it indicates the necessary security infrastructure. Figure 1 below shows the interdependencies of WP2 with Work Packages.

Figure 1 Work Packages Interdependencies

Figure 2 WP2 Tasks interdependencies.

1.3. Structure of the Deliverable

The document is structured as follows:

- Section 1 includes the introduction and context of the document
- Section 2 presents the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) under which the privacy hazard assessment was conducted
- Section 3 describes the Security and Privacy assessment projected to be carried out by use case and per pilot
- Section 4 includes the security mechanisms proposed to mitigate the aforementioned threats
- Section 5 provides a summary as well as the conclusions of this Deliverable

2. General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)

This section provides a brief description of the GDPR, that will provide the guidelines for the privacy assessment conducted within the activities of this task. The EU approved a new legal framework for law enforcement and police in April 2016: the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) [1] and the Data Protection Directive. The GDPR, which went into effect on May 25th, 2018, is the world's most comprehensive and advanced data protection regulation, capable of dealing with the implications of the digital age.

The GDPR places a strong emphasis on data integrity and confidentiality. Personal data must be treated in such a way that they are protected from unauthorized or unlawful processing, as well as accidental loss, destruction, or damage, both inside and outside of the EU.

Failure to comply with GDPR rules might result in a significant administrative penalty of up to 20 million euros, or 4% of the preceding year's annual global turnover.

2.1. The 8 rights of a Data Subject indicated by GDPR

According to the regulation, individuals also have authority on how companies utilize information that is directly related to them personally, and they have eight particular rights. Some of these rights are brand new, while others are enhanced versions of existing EU Data Protection Directive rights. These rights are referred to as "Rights of Data Subjects" in GDPR.

In contrast with data "objects", data subjects are active entities. Namely, they do have to decide whether or not they consent with any modification or utilization of their personal data. They are the sole proprietors of their data and have complete control over how it is utilized.

In Figure 3 the 8 rights that are granted to any user that acts as a data subject under the GDPR, are depicted.

Figure 3 The 8 rights of a Data Subject [2]

More specifically, every right indicated by GDPR is described in detail, below:

- **The Right to Be Informed:** Before the data collection, any data subject may know what kind of their personal data is collected, the reason of its collection, as well as the entity that collected it and with whom it may be shared. Moreover, they may acknowledge the time duration of its storage and the ways they can file a complaint. It is very important that all the aforementioned information should be available in plain and clear language.
- **The Right of Access:** After the data collection, users may submit access requests, in order to acquire information from a company/organization, concerning the processing of their personal data. In other

words, they may require information about the way their data was collected, processed, stored, and again what kind of their personal data are collected and the reason they were collected.

- **The Right to Rectification:** Data subjects have the right to ask their personal data update, in case there are any inaccuracies or incomplete data collection. The company/organization have a month-long deadline, to respond.
- **The Right to Object to Processing:** Users are allowed to object to the processing of their personal data, in case a company/organization has no explicit consent to. Furthermore, the users have the right to stop their personal data from being used for direct marketing purposes.
- **The Right to Restrict Processing:** Data subjects are allowed to block or minimize personal data being processed under specific circumstances.
- **The Right to Data Portability:** Data subjects may obtain or move their personal data that they have already offered, to another company/organization, in a structured, commonly used, and machine-readable format.
- **The Right to Be Forgotten:** Also known as the Right to Erasure, it gives data subjects the ability to demand their personal data to be permanently deleted. Moreover, the organization that receives the request should also notify any other company/organisation with whom they have shared the data, in order for them to also delete it.
- **Rights in Relation to Automated Decision Making and Profiling:** Data subjects have the right to request human intervention, instead of being subject to automated decision making and profiling. This is applicable when the decision-making produces an effect that affects the data subjects, legally.

2.2. Data Security principles

Among the indications included in the Data Security section of GDPR, there are two very crucial points, that are directly linked to the technical security design of a system. According to the GDPR companies/organizations should use encryption or pseudonymization/anonymization techniques, whenever it is possible [3]. The first one concerns the data management. In other words, it involves techniques that are applied for data “masking” purposes, such as pseudonymization, anonymization and encryption. Pseudonymization refers to the procedure during which, information identifying attributes of a data entry within a dataset are replaced with at least one aliases or pseudonyms, for data management and de-identification purposes [3]. The difference between pseudonymization and anonymization processed, lies in whether it is classified as personal data or not. Pseudonymous data can still be re-identified in some way (even if it's indirect and remote), whereas anonymous data can't. Anonymisation techniques are not the same as pseudonymisation approaches. When data is anonymized, any information that could be used to identify a data subject is removed. Pseudonymisation does not eliminate all identifying information from data; rather, it minimizes the dataset's linkability to an individual's original identity (e.g., via an encryption scheme) [4]. Figure 4 depicts this difference. Encryption aims in data security through at least one mathematical technique. During encryption, the information is being encoded and the original plaintext is transformed to a ciphertext, an encrypted format that there is no way to extract information from. The purpose of encryption is to allow only authorized entities to decode the ciphertext, and have access to the actual information. This is commonly achieved, with the use of a secret “key”, that it is known only to the entrusted parties. Thus, a third-party interceptor cannot actually access the information.

DATA DEIDENTIFICATION

Figure 4 Anonymization vs Pseudonymization [5]

The second part of the statement, refers to the techniques that were described, and applied whenever it is possible. In order to further understand this indication, one should take into consideration, all the forms that data may take, and all the phases that data goes through during the system processes. More specifically, data should be protected both in storage and during communication. Moreover, if it is feasible, data should be in an anonymized or encrypted form, even throughout the data processing procedures, that might take place. This results in a robust and secure system, that minimizes the risk of a successful cyberattack or a data breach. However, it should be noted that such mechanisms prevent access to the original information, they are not a mean to prevent attackers from actually intercept a communication, or accessing the system sources. Instead, they make sure that even after a malicious manages to intercept or access the system source, the data that they may collect are not in readable or/and they cannot be linked to a data subject.

3. Security and Privacy Assessment

The assessment conducted for this task is based on the Regulatory Recommendations for Privacy, Data Protection and Cyber-Security in the Data Protection Impact Assessment Template for Smart Grid and Smart Metering [6]. For the purposes of this deliverable, the assessment is presented as it will be shared per pilot and per use-case, in order to gather information about the threats present in each of them, and then, in the Deliverable D2.6-Report on cybersecurity framework design & specifications for data protection & privacy v2, there will be a comparative presentation of the assessment conducted before and after the implementations of the security framework. The methodology for this assessment is presented in section 3.2 of this deliverable. Use cases should be taken into consideration, when conducting the assessment, to have a perspective of any stakeholder that is involved per use case, as well as the type of chain processes that may be present.

A simplified version of the template provided in [6] will be communicated with all involved partners, i.e. pilot partners and technology partners as well, aiming to collect information concerning possible vulnerabilities of the systems, as well as to calculate the potential risk in every pilot. The assessment is necessary to design the security mechanisms that will effectively protect the system.

Section 3.1 gives a brief description of the use cases tested in the context of the ACCEPT project, while section 3.2 analyses the process followed to perform the DPIA. Finally, Section 3.3 concentrates specifically in the assessment conducted on the pilots of the ACCEPT project.

The Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) process questionnaires are listed in the *****ANNEXES*****, in the end of the deliverable.

3.1. Use Cases tested in the ACCEPT project

In this section a brief description of the use cases tested in the context of the ACCEPT project. The security and privacy hazard assessment is conducted per use case tested. All use cases have been reported and analysed thoroughly in Deliverable D2.1- ACCEPT business scenarios, use cases & requirements [7]. Table 2 summarizes the use cases tested.

Table 2 ACCEPT Use Cases

UC1	Monitoring and Visualization of Metering & Sensor Energy Data in community buildings
UC2	Building self-consumption employing Virtual Thermal Energy Storage optimisation
UC3	Consumer demand-side flexibility forecasting and optimisation taking into account comfort boundaries, activity patterns and possible requirements
UC4	Demand elasticity profiling-forecasting-aggregation and analysis in community level
UC5	Intra-day district-level DER flexibility management for community self-balancing
UC6	Day-ahead smart charging flexibility quantification via EV usage pattern profiling and forecasting
UC7	Community-level P2P flexibility/ energy exchange based on locally produced renewable energy
UC8	Participation in explicit Demand Response schemes
UC9	Participation in implicit Demand Response schemes
UC10	Community flexibility bundling for local congestion management service
UC11	Retailer day-ahead optimal pricing configuration for aggregated portfolio balancing
UC12	Optimal scheduling and operation of heating generation for a cost-efficient district-level DER management
UC13	Increase self-consumption at local community level
UC14	Active Citizen and LEC Engagement

Following there is a short Description of each use case mentioned.

- UC1: Precise measurement and quantification of flexibility requires precise collection of data while ensuring a secure and seamless information flow across components and actors. The necessary hardware will consist of market available components and off-the-self sensory and measuring equipment that will operate under a common software stack.
- UC2: This Use Case (UC) deals with the optimal scheduling of operation for HVAC resources at building/apartment level, combined with the heat energy storage capabilities offered by the building envelope or hot water storage tanks, so as to increase the consumption of self-generated electricity via renewable resources. Consequently, the UC's objective is also to minimize the dependence of a single consumer from the grid, by making him/her self-sufficient.
- UC3: The Use Case (UC) captures one of the core functionalities to be provided by the on-demand Flexibility Management component of the ACCEPT solution. In order for consumers to participate into energy markets, it is necessary to be able to provide forecasts of their baseline demand, as well as any upwards or downwards regulations of this baseline that can be provided, at specific future time intervals. The process depends on the modelling of the characteristics of the building, combined with the installed heating/cooling, resources DHW and other small electrical resources, as well as the modelling of the occupants' behaviour. Both of the above are translated into mathematical constraints that allow the execution of a number of numerical optimizations, that yield the quantitative forecasts in terms of baseline and flexibility offered by the asset.
- UC4: Demand elasticity profiling-forecasting-aggregation and analysis at community level followed by consumption pattern optimisation through price signalling. The main goal is to capture consumers' behaviour and at the same time optimize the amount of energy needed for the whole market. The optimization process would start by analysing profiles, deploying pricing schemes and evaluate consumers' response.
- UC5: Distributed energy resources (DER) are becoming more relevant in electric power systems, and the main challenge at the distribution level consists in the optimal orchestration of all assets to provide the best load/generation distribution and from a more user-oriented perspective consider the economic impact caused by the dynamic pricing scheme.
- UC6: EV charging, is a very demanding energy consumption. It is also one of the few that are dispatchable. Thus, it can prove quite useful, when contemplating demand-side management schemes, especially at an aggregated level, such as the one in an energy community.
- UC7: Optimization of consumption and production on a community level requires close cooperation between individuals. P2P exchange of energy/flexibility in a fair and transparent way can increase cooperation by optimally sharing common renewable sources.
- UC8: Provide DR events at both LEC Level and end-user level, in order to provide appropriate services to the electricity market.
- UC9: Provide optimal DR signals to the LEC assets available, without raising the end-users' discomfort above agreed or acceptable levels.
- UC10: This use case covers the development of a tool that allows flexibility of distribution network assets at the district level for storage and generation and all the other district assets and at the user level for demand to avoid or mitigate network congestion.
- UC11: Customer's behaviour profiling-forecasting-aggregation by deploying day-ahead pricing strategies, DER estimated production and analysis in community level followed by pricing method optimisation through price signalling while ensuring portfolio balancing.
- UC12: The development and implementation of an optimal operating schedule for district heating equipment can provide an additional layer of cost-saving flexibility to the urban energy consumption structure by leveraging the predictive and data-flow capabilities of today's smart grids.

- UC13: The use case concentrates on the optimization of use of heating/cooling devices at district/community level, so that energy generated by renewable DERs is not wasted but utilised optimally to satisfy the user needs and reduce the amount of purchased energy from the grid. In addition, it stipulates the coordination of building and district energy resources to achieve the same objective, extended to cover the energy needs of the whole community, which is considered a single entity/actor.
- UC14: Rather than a traditional unidirectional top-down approach when implementing renewable energy solutions, active citizen and Local Energy Community (LEC) engagement aims to establish a meaningful two-way communication with members of the community and the operating manager/owner of energy distribution networks (e.g., DSO). Research into LECs through community mapping and analysis of needs, motivations and potential barriers is undertaken to implement effective engagement strategies to establish a long-term bottom-up and community-led discussion on the issues surrounding the active involvement of consumers/prosumers and LECs in the energy transition and the integration of large amount of RES in local areas.
Due to the unique characteristics of each community, the specific factors impacting active citizen and LEC engagement, including the stakeholders involved and/or affected, strategies for engagement cannot be predetermined. There will always be influencing factors that will be unknown before engagements start. Therefore, the complete description section below is based on a previous case study to illustrate the process utilised in this UC and given the complexities involved in engaging with communities it is not to be interpreted as a complete description of actions to be used in ACCEPT.

3.2. Process followed to perform the DPIA

In this section, there is a thorough description of the six different phases that the Data Privacy Impact Assessment (DPIA) process can be separated in.

3.2.1. First Phase: Identifying the reason(s) for performing a DPIA

Conducting a DPIA aims to assess the potential security and privacy hazards, which are present during any kind of data handling. According to the ACCEPT project restrictions and guidelines, all systems should respect the GDPR and measures should be taken to secure all communications that take place within the ACCEPT system framework. Processing methods, such as the employment of new technologies or the data collection and handling, that are used to satisfy the requirements of each use case run the risk of infringing on people's rights and privacy. The processing of sensitive/personal data on a wide scale, as well as the systematic and detailed processing of personal attributes, such as profiling, intensifies the need to design a robust security framework, in order to ensure that any stakeholder affected per use case, maintains their privacy. Even if only one of the criteria is met in every circumstance, a DPIA is advised.

As it is explicitly mentioned in the EU GPDR Compliant: "Article 35 outlines some situations in which a DPIA is mandatory. Such a case is when you are processing large scale of special categories of data, or any personal data that relates to criminal convictions. Also, if the processing is based on automated decision making, including profiling a DPIA is necessary. The last case outlined in Article 35 is when there is systematic monitoring of a publicly accessible area on a large scale [3]".

An effective DPIA should benefit both the participating individuals within a project and the organization that is responsible for it. It is typically the most effective way to demonstrate to the Information Commissioner's Officer how personal data processing conforms with data protection regulations, even though it is not a legal necessity.

A project that has undergone a DPIA should be less intrusive to individuals' privacy and hence less likely to have a negative impact. A DPIA should increase transparency and make it simpler for people to understand how and why their data is utilized.

Below the advantages after having the DPIA methodology implemented are listed:

- Minimizing the cost that is due to system redesign or process readjustment through the mitigation of Risks to Privacy and Personal Data;
- Ensuring that there are no project dismissals, through the mapping of any crucial Risks present, in advance.
- Promoting adherence to the Data Minimization and Accuracy principles;
- Making it easier for companies to make decisions based on the DPIA report

- Boosting customer, employee, and citizen confidence by demonstrating GDPR compliance, privacy respect, and a commitment to ensuring personal data protection
- Raising public awareness of the risk of losing credibility due to a perceived data breach or a failure to satisfy requirements in terms of personal data security.

3.2.2. Second Phase: The Set-Up

According to DPIA guidelines, each organization should indicate a team responsible for the conducted DPIA, i.e. a DPIA team. To join the DPIA team, one must have a thorough grasp of the project, as well as knowledge of Privacy and Data Protection, Cyber Security, but also experience doing risk assessments and especially privacy impact assessments. The options that the team conducting the DPIA has, are shown in Figure 5 Options available for the DPIA team. This is also the list of options that is available to every pilot partner that conducts their own DPIA, in the ACCEPT project.

A	B	C
Please indicate whether DPIA will be performed by: (i) a dedicated DPIA team, (ii) a third party, (iii) the persons in charge of the Process/ Project		
1		
2		
3	Explanation:	
4	Option I : A dedicated team within the organisation, but not the one in charge of the Smart Grids or Smart Metering application:	
5	Option Ia - employees with knowledge of the automation environment (hardware, software, networks and network components);	
6	Option Ib - employees in the user environment;	
7	Option Ic - the Data Protection Officer could be involved as advisor to this team from an independent role.	
8	Option II : a third party providing an external expertise needed for the DPIA	
9	Option III : the persons in charge of the application/system which is the target of the DPIA. This might especially apply in the case of SME's with limited resources.	
10		
11		
12		
13	DPIA will be performed by:	

Figure 5 Options available for the DPIA team

Project documents such as deliverables and reports, documentation, functional and non-functional requirements, and use cases architecture are all required sources for conducting the DPIA for the ACCEPT project. Furthermore, Pilot Partners conducting the DPIA should consult the International Standards and Technical Reports on which the DPIA methodology is based, taking into account the sort of data to be collected and the intended application.

3.2.3. Third Phase: Use Case Analysis

The goal of this phase is to establish the DPIA's scope and limits, as well as to offer a detailed description of the assets covered by the DPIA. The Data Controller should collect thorough information on the use of Personal Data in the business activities involved in ACCEPT project.

Actors are any components that take part in the Use Cases; as a result, an Actor is where Personal Data are stored and Personal Data Processing actions take place. The DPIA's Assets are the Personal Data that are assigned to certain Actors discovered through the analysis of Scenarios. The major result of the Third Phase of the DPIA is the detection and characterization of assets.

The Characterization of Actors and Assets per Pilot Site is defined in the excel sheet that corresponds to Figure 6 below where the structure of the specific excel form is shown.

REPORT ON CYBERSECURITY FRAMEWORK DESIGN & SPECIFICATIONS FOR DATA PROTECTION & PRIVACY V1

Asset	Actor Name (physical component)	Actor Type	Actor description (e.g., Where does Personal Data Processing Operations occur?)	How many data subjects for that Personal Data reside in each Actor instance?	Retention Time within Actor		Data Controller (physical person in the internal team)	Data Processor (physical person in the internal team)
					How long are they kept within the Actor?	How frequently are Personal Data accessed?		

Figure 6 Asset and Actor identification and characterization Form.

In detail for every Asset the information required to complete the excel form is:

- Actor Name (Physical Component)
- Actor Type
- Actor description (e.g., Where does Personal Data Processing Operations occur?)
- How many data subjects for that Personal Data reside in each Actor instance?
- Retention Time within Actor
 - How long are they kept within the Actor?
 - How frequently are Personal Data accessed?
- Data Controller (physical person in the internal team)
- Data Processor (physical person in the internal team)

The options available for the Actor Types field are listed in the **Error! Reference source not found.** below.

Table 3 Actor Types Options

Actor Type	Description
System	referring to device/appliance
Application	SW application or IT component
Role	referring to individual
Organization	referring to entire organization – external actors

3.2.4. Fourth Phase: Threat Identification

Stakeholders' rights are primarily threatened due to Threats impacting Assets in such a way, that might result in an undesirable occurrence. The approach begins by determining the severity of a collection of Threats that influence Assets. Threats were specified in an excel file disseminated by CERTH, as illustrated in the red framed area in Figure 7. Each Threat Category should have one or more Assets linked with it.

***** The Threat Categories identified are available in ANNEX I - Threats affecting Assets.*****

Step 4			Step 5			
Threat Category affecting Primary Assets TC(PA)		Asset	Severity at PA level	Severity at TC level	Likelihood at PA level	Likelihood at TC level
Illegitimate processing of Personal Data				0		1
PossibleThreats						
<input type="checkbox"/>	No lawfulness of processing					
<input type="checkbox"/>	Collection exceeding purpose					
<input type="checkbox"/>	Unclear responsibilities for Data Processing.					
<input type="checkbox"/>	The protection of data is compromised outside the European Economic Area (EEA).					
<input type="checkbox"/>	<i>If other, please specify below</i>					

Figure 7 Excel sheet for completing phases four and five

3.2.5. Fifth Phase: Risk Assessment

The Threat Category's influence on individual rights and freedoms is weighted in the Risk Level. The Likelihood of the linked Threats becoming real is considered in the Risk Level.

The blue framed area in Figure 7 shows how the Assessment of Severity and Likelihood on Asset Level (PA) was defined in an excel file. The Severity & Likelihood Scale, which can be found in ***ANNEX II - Severity & Likelihood Scale***, was used to determine severity and likelihood. According to the highest value of Severity and Likelihood in Asset level, Severity and Likelihood at Threat Category (TC) level is automatically produced.

Finally, on Sheet Summary of Risk Level (Risk Level/Priority map), which will be discussed in Section 3.2.6, the Final Risk Level and the map that reflects the final risk level of threat categories impacting Assets are acquired.

3.2.6. Sixth Phase: Risk Treatment and Final Resolution

The goal at this phase is to review and analyse the risks identified and assessed in the preceding one, as well as to show whatever controls have been applied, or are scheduled to be implemented, to decrease risk to acceptable levels. Each identified risk must be properly mitigated in accordance with the procedures listed in ***ANNEX III - List of possible controls***, taking into account the Severity Indicators.

The term "residual risk" refers to the risk that remains after a risk has been mitigated. In this case, the Data Controller must define the Residual Risks that still exist after the controls have been implemented.

Each Asset's risk treatment and residual severity / likelihood should be defined, and the Residual Severity & Likelihood at Threat Category Level was automatically produced in the excel file that CERTH will disseminate. Figure 8 depicts the excel form for such purposes.

Threat Category affecting Primary Assets TC(PA)	Asset	Step 6					
		Initial Severity at PA level	Residual Severity at PA level	Initial Severity at TC level	Residual Severity at TC level	Initial Likelihood at PA level	Residual Likelihood at PA level
Illegitimate processing of Personal Data	0	0		0	0	0	
Possible Risk Treatment	0	0				0	
<input type="checkbox"/> Managing Contracts between Data Controllers and Data Processors	0	0				0	
<input type="checkbox"/> Managing third parties with legitimate access to Personal Data	0	0				0	
<input type="checkbox"/> Monitoring logical access controls	0	0				0	
<input type="checkbox"/> Partitioning Personal Data	0	0				0	
<input type="checkbox"/> Encrypting Personal Data	0	0				0	
<input type="checkbox"/> Anonymizing Personal Data	0	0				0	
<input type="checkbox"/> Managing Personal Data violations	0	0				0	
<input type="checkbox"/> No collection of identifiable information, only pseudonyms, or anonym data	0	0				0	
<input type="checkbox"/> Active measures to preclude the use of particular data-items in the making of particular decisions	0	0				0	
<input type="checkbox"/> Limits on the use of information for a very specific purpose, with strong legal, organisational and technical safeguards preventing its application to any other purpose	0	0				0	
<input type="checkbox"/> Active measures to preclude the disclosure of particular data-items	0	0				0	
<input type="checkbox"/> Minimisation of Personal Data retention by destroying it as soon as the transaction for which it is needed is completed	0	0				0	
<input type="checkbox"/> Destruction schedules for personal information	0	0	0			0	0
<input type="checkbox"/> Use of mathematical methods without collecting and registration source data to reach goals	0	0	0			0	0
<input type="checkbox"/> Audit	0	0	0			0	0
<input type="checkbox"/> If other, please specify, below:	0	0	0			0	0

Figure 8 Residual Severity at Asset Level and Threat Category Level form

Lastly, a map that is automatically generated, depicts the Final Risk Level of Threat Categories that influence Assets, first with the Initial Risk Level in terms of Severity and Likelihood, and then with the Residual Risk Level in terms of Residual Severity and Likelihood.

This process is intended to produce a list of planned and implemented Asset Risk Mitigation Controls, as well as a revised risk map with residual hazards identified. In theory, compared to the previous risk map with no restrictions, this new risk map should have reduced Residual Risks.

Table 4 provides a description of the Risk levels, as it is attached to the circulated excel file.

Table 4 Risk Levels Analysis

Risk Level	Description
1. Risks with a maximum / significant Severity and Likelihood	These risks must be absolutely avoided or reduced by implementing controls that reduce both their Severity and their Likelihood. Ideally, care should even be taken to ensure that they are treated by independent controls of prevention (actions taken prior to a damaging event), protection (actions taken during a damaging event) and recovery (actions taken after a damaging event)
2. Risks with a maximum/significant/moderate Severity but a negligible/limited/moderate Likelihood	These risks must be avoided or reduced by implementing controls that reduce both their Severity and their Likelihood. Emphasis must be placed on preventive controls. These risks can be taken, but only if it is shown that it is not possible to reduce their Severity and if their Likelihood is negligible
3. Risks with a negligible/limited Severity but a maximum/significant/moderate Likelihood and risks with a negligible/limited/moderate Severity but a maximum/significant Likelihood	These risks must be reduced by implementing controls that reduce their Likelihood. Emphasis must be placed on recovery controls. These risks can be taken, but only if it is shown that it is not possible to reduce their Likelihood and if their Severity is negligible
4. Risks with a negligible/limited Severity and Likelihood	It should be possible to take these risks, especially since the treatment of other risks should also lead to their treatment

3.3. Process to be followed for all ACCEPT pilots-use cases

This section concentrated mainly on the assessment conducted for the ACCEPT pilots.

Within ACCEPT, CERTH, as T2.5 leader, indicated the following steps to all involved partners (pilot and technology partners):

- Lead a Webinar in the DPIA template, which included a guideline paper and an excel document as a template, for all pilot leaders (together with key technology suppliers).
- Each pilot leader will be asked to complete the DPIA report (assisted by CERTH, if any further guidance was requested).
- CERTH will compile the final results of all reports received from the various trial sites.
- CERTH will propose mitigation measures to alleviate found threats.
- The DPIA findings will be reported by **all related** partners and disseminated.

4. Proposed Measures for Threat Mitigation

In this section, the measures proposed for the mitigation of the threats identified, using the DPIA method presented in Section 3. After a preliminary contact with the pilot and technology partners involved within the ACCEPT project, it became clear that the design of a security framework would be challenging due to the diversity, in terms of security needs, that appears among the pilots. The infrastructure of each pilot has different vulnerabilities and weak points, and there are different communication protocols used. Moreover, as the system design is still under development (Task T2.3), more detailed information will be provided within the second version of this deliverable.

The proposed security framework focuses in two main axes, data subject protection and data protection. Both axes have multiple areas of application. In other words, both procedures concern protecting the data subjects and data respectively, in all forms and in all stages of the process. Thus, in the following sections there are some methods presented that aim to preserve users' privacy, and at the same time to maintain the information confidentiality.

4.1. Data Communication Protection

As it is vital to safeguard stored data, it is also necessary to protect data exchanged over the network. When data is exchanged, the risk for a potential attack is elevated.

Communication security (COMSEC) is the protection of private and sensitive data from unauthorized parties / interceptors with the goal of denying access to valuable information. Unauthorized parties are prevented from acquiring information arising from the interception and analysis of our communications by four elements of communications security:

- Cryptographic Protection. Protection of cryptography (encryption / decryption) systems used for data protection, providing technically accurate cryptosystems and their proper use
- Emissions Security (EMSEC). Measures made to prevent unauthorized individuals from gaining access to important data derived from the interception of communication systems and the interception and analysis of compromising emanations from cryptographic equipment and information systems.
- Transmission Security (TRANSEC). Protection of data transmission from interception and exploitation by means other than cryptanalysis, protection of data when transmitted by the parties
- Physical Security. Physical measures necessary to protect classified equipment, materials and information from access or observation by unauthorized parties

Data encryption is one of the most effective data protection technologies for both data in transit and data at rest. Sensitive data is frequently encrypted before being transferred, and/or encrypted connections are utilized to protect the contents of data in transit. An example of the way encryption/decryption of transferred data can be used to prevent attacks such as eavesdropping on a communication channel, is depicted in Figure 9 below.

Figure 9 Data in transit encryption benefits

When using secure communication methods like Transport Layer Security (TLS) or a Virtual Private Network (VPN), one may rest assured that the content of a conversation will not be intercepted if the technology is effectively implemented. As cybercriminals develop new ways to breach networks and steal data, it's more important than ever to protect sensitive data in transit and at rest.

4.1.1. ACCEPT implementation

In the context of the ACCEPT project, all data communications will be secured using encryption algorithms. The use of some known secure protocols is already established, as certain pilots are using HTTPS when applicable. However, the ACCEPT SEAC framework guidelines refer to all kind of communication protocols that may be present, and are still under investigation. The most basic step taken to ensure the data-in-transit security, is the implementation of the TLS protocol on the communication channels.

The TLS protocol is widely used to secure network communications, mainly client-server ones, from eavesdropping and tampering attacks. The use of the protocol is not obligatory. Hence, there needs to be a specific request from the communication initiator for a TLS-protected conversation [8]. This is often achieved, a separate port for TLS communication, like port 443 which is used for encrypted HTTPS communication, or alternatively, there also can be a protocol-specific request like the STARTTLS, in the case of electronic mail or news protocols.

- After the use of TLS is requested, in order to establish the secured communication, a negotiation using a negotiation procedure, is followed [9]. The first phase includes an asymmetric algorithm that is used only for the exchange of the key of another symmetric algorithm, that will be used for the encryption of the rest of the communication. The handshake procedure starts with a client requesting a TLS-enabled communication, communicating also which cipher and hash functions they support
- The server makes a choice for a cipher and a hash function respectively, and announces it to the client. Also, it uses a digital certificate as a proof of identity
- Client checks this certification validity to decide whether the communication will proceed
- There is a crypto-challenge between the client and the server following, which concludes to the encryption key generation and sharing. The key sharing procedure is secure as no malicious attacker can access the key due to the asymmetric, and also reliable, as there is no possibility that there will be an undetected altering of the data during the procedure

If any of the aforementioned phases is not completed properly, the TLS handshake fails, and the communication is aborted. Figure 10 below depicts the handshake steps.

Connections that are TLS protected are characterized by at least of one of the following properties:

- The communication is considered protected due to the usage of symmetric encryption algorithm. The keys for this algorithm are generated in the first or handshake phase. The exchange of any actual information is performed only after the first phase is completed successfully
- Identity authentication of the two end-points can be achieved through public-key encryption algorithms, however it is only obligatory, for the server side [10].
- Every message exchanged has attached an integrity check bit sequence, to ensure that there is no data loss that is undetected, and that there is no data modification, during the transmission [11].

Figure 10 TLS Handshake Steps

As all pilot sites architecture is still under development, some of the communication protocols that will be used are not defined. In case there are communications using protocols where TCP is not supported, more information about the security mechanism implemented will be included in the Deliverable D2.6-Report on cybersecurity framework design & specifications for data protection & privacy v2.

4.2. Data Subject Protection

As analyzed in Section 2, the GDPR extensively describes a list of data subject rights, along with some strong recommendations concerning the methods to use, for the preservation of the aforementioned rights. In order to preserve the anonymity of the users that are involved in each use case, as well as their personal data privacy, implementing anonymization techniques is highly recommended. The next section presents different anonymization techniques and describes their purpose.

4.2.1. Anonymization purposes and techniques

Data anonymization as its name by itself implies, concerns the protection of a subject that is linked to some piece of information. According to [12] its definition is a "process by which personal data is altered in such a way that a data subject can no longer be identified directly or indirectly, either by the data controller alone or in collaboration with any other party". Data anonymization necessitates a thorough grasp of the following components, which should be taken into account when selecting appropriate anonymization procedures and level.

Figure 11 Anonymisation Process [13]

First of all, anonymization's purpose and utility. As anonymization should be done particularly for the purpose at hand, the aim of anonymization should be obvious. Regardless of the approaches used, the anonymisation procedure decreases the original information in the dataset to some amount. As a result, as the level of anonymization increases, the dataset's utility, such as precision, decreases. Thus, there should be an analysis on the level of the trade-off between acceptable utility and reducing the risk of re-identification, which occurs when a data subject is identified through data that was supposed to be anonymous. In addition, anonymisation technique characteristics should be taken into consideration. The diverse properties of anonymisation techniques mean that some techniques may be more fit for a circumstance than others. For example, some approaches (such as character masking) are typically used on direct identifiers whereas others (such as aggregation) are typically used on indirect identifiers. The various anonymisation approaches alter data in a variety of ways. Some only change parts of an attribute (e.g. character masking) while others update the value of an attribute across several records (e.g. aggregation). Moreover, some processes replace the entire attribute with unrelated but consistent information (e.g. pseudonymization) and even remove the attribute entirely (e.g. attribute suppression). Last but not least, information that may be inferred from anonymized data are to be taken into account, too. Certain information can be inferred from anonymized data. Masking, for example, may conceal personal information but not the length of the original material in terms of characters. The problem of Inference isn't confined to a single characteristic; it can affect multiple attributes, even if they've all been anonymized. As a result, before deciding on the actual procedures and after implementing the techniques, the anonymisation process must consider all possibilities.

Table 5 **Error! Reference source not found.** summarizes the anonymization techniques along with a brief description of their key features.

Table 5 Anonymization Techniques

Anonymization Technique	Key features
Attribute Suppression	The process includes the deletion of an entire feature of an entry in a dataset, an equivalent to a "column" in a datasheet.
Record Suppression	This technique concerns the elimination of an entire entry in a dataset. It results in multiple attribute modification at once.
Character masking	The technique concerns the alternation of specific characters of an attribute value, for instance with the use of a constant symbol such as "x". It is a mostly partial process, as usually only part of the attribute's characters is altered.
Pseudonymisation	The technique refers to the replacement of the data that act as key identifiers, with aliases also known as "pseudonyms". It can be both a reversible and non-reversible process.
Generalisation	During generalisation, also known as recoding, the precision of several attributes is reduced, through the replacement of the original value with a more obscure value, like a data range.
Swapping	Swapping refers to the "shuffling" of the entries of a dataset, in order for all attribute values to still be present, but not linked to the original data subject.
Data Perturbation	After Data Perturbations applied, certain attribute values are replaced with values that are slightly divergent from the original ones.
Data Aggregation	This technique replaces original attribute values, with a list of summarized values, resulting in a reduced dataset.

4.2.2. Homomorphic Encryption

Homomorphic encryption is a type of encryption that permits particular sorts of computations on ciphertexts to produce an encrypted result that, when decoded, is the exact same with the result of the corresponding operations on the plaintexts. Figure 12 How Homomorphic Schemes operate depicts that scheme. There is no secret key knowledge requirement. In current communication system designs, this is a desired characteristic. Homomorphic encryption may be vaguely considered as an extension of the wider public-key encryption family. In order to understand this, one should consider the relative "homomorphism" term, in algebra. A homomorphism indicates a special correspondence among the elements of two different algebraic. This correspondence can be translated as the arising of the same in result, when the same operation is applied in the two groups. Hence, homomorphic encryption could be thought as a homomorphism that is observed in the two special groups of the encrypted and the unencrypted texts. Homomorphic encryption encompasses a variety of encryption techniques that allow different sorts of computations to be performed on enciphered data [14]. The computations are expressed as arithmetic or Boolean circuits.

One of the most known cryptographic algorithms with homomorphic features is the RSA. In detail, RSA is multiplicatively homomorphic [15], as it can be seen below

$$c_1 = m_1^e \pmod{q} \text{ and } c_2 = m_2^e \pmod{q}$$

Where q is the product of two large prime numbers and e satisfies the condition $\gcd(e, \phi(q)) = 1$. Thus:

$$c_3 = c_1 * c_2 = m_1^e * m_2^e \pmod{q} = (m_1 * m_2)^e \pmod{q} \equiv m_1 * m_2$$

Although, aiming to increase the algorithms security, RSA is enhanced with the random bit padding, that takes place right-before the encryption process begins. This results in the loss of the aforementioned homomorphic feature.

In general, encryption algorithms can be separated in the following categories:

- Partially Homomorphic: This category includes schemes that present a homomorphic feature, only in a certain type of operation, such as multiplication

- Somewhat Homomorphic: These algorithms present homomorphic features, both in addition and multiplication, however these are limited up to a certain complexity, meaning up to a specific number of operations
- Fully Homomorphic: The algorithms contained in this category, present homomorphic feature in both multiplication and addition, and have no limitation in the number of operations that may be performed

Figure 12 How Homomorphic Schemes operate

The multiplicative depth of operations is the fundamental practical restriction in conducting calculations over encrypted data, for the majority of homomorphic encryption methods. Homomorphic encryption systems offer inferior security characteristics than non-homomorphic methods in terms of malleability. Malleability describes the ability to alter an encrypted text that will result in a correspondingly altered plain text when decrypted. Because messages may be deliberately changed by a malicious user, malleability is usually seen to be a bad characteristic for message integrity. Homomorphic encryption methods, on the other hand, are designed to be malleable, allowing authorized parties to change encrypted text without knowing the message's contents. That is, they can alter an encrypted stream without being required to decrypt and re-encrypt it, and even in case they don't have the means to decrypt it.

Homomorphic Encryption benefits concern both data privacy leveraging and overall security robustness. In particular:

- Homomorphic encryption allows organizations/companies to use cloud computing and storage services in a secure manner. It minimizes the need to choose between data security and usability. To protect the privacy of data, there is no need to conceal or remove any data elements. Without jeopardizing privacy, every characteristic may be used in an analysis. Organizations/companies are not obligated to employ cloud services for the protection of their sensitive data and at the same time, they are still able to compute on it.
- Cooperation is promoted by the enabling of companies to communicate sensitive business data with external parties without exposing the data or the calculation results. This can help to speed up cooperation and creativity while reducing the danger of sensitive data being compromised.
- It ensures regulatory compliance, namely it can enable organizations/companies in highly regulated areas, such under the GDPR law, to outsource research and analytical services without risking noncompliance.
- Fully Homomorphic encryption is also resistant in quantum attacks

On the other hand, there are some important drawbacks when applying homomorphic encryption. The most limiting factor, is the weak performance. More specifically, fully homomorphic encryption is too demanding, in terms of resource needs, in case of high complexity operations. Namely there is a big trade-off between accuracy and computational speed. Moreover, it should be taken into consideration that the homomorphic encryption is more of a security measure rather than a privacy one. It contributes to the overall system security, thus it should be a part of a more complete security design.

In the context of the ACCEPT project, homomorphic encryption is highly recommended, as it will contribute in the data privacy needs, and at the same time it will enhance the compliance to the GDPR law. It can be implemented as an alternative for an anonymization technique. In order to narrow down the limitations that are brought up with the use of homomorphic encryption, it is planned to implement a Partially or Somewhat Homomorphic scheme, instead of a Fully homomorphic one. As the main contribution of these algorithms is the ability to operate on encrypted data, without having access to the actual information, these also translates in the data subject protection, although in quite the opposite way of the classic anonymization techniques; While anonymization contemplates about applying techniques to protect the identity of the data subject, homomorphic encryption gives the ability to completely mask the actual information, hence not permitting any connection between a data subject and the respective private information. Furthermore, this allows not only the encryption of the data under processing but also to the stored ones, as there is no need to have actual access to information, that is only intended for calculation purposes. In the next section, a State-of-the-Art analysis on the current applications of Homomorphic Encryption, is presented.

4.2.3. State-of-the-Art Analysis

In early stages of Fully Homomorphic Encryption (FHE) research, researchers focused on lattice-based schemes. FHE security schemes including lattice-based ones, are based on hard problems related to lattices. When a crypto-algorithm is based on lattices, the process required to compromise it, is similar to solving specific difficult computational problems on lattices, for example the Sparse Subset Sum Problem and the Shortest Vector Problem. The work of [16], [17], [18], describe such lattice-based schemes, which included considerably long public key sizes and ciphertext sizes. In order to enhance efficiency and be able to parallelise tasks, researchers in [19] proposed Single Instruction Multiple Data (SIMD) techniques. The researchers on [20], [21], [22] are concentrating on Learning With Errors (LWE) and Ring Learning With Errors (RLWE) based FHE. As far as LWE is concerned, studies shown to be as complicated as the worst-case lattice problems. There was an extension of this problem to work over rings [23] and this caused an efficiency increase of LWE. Lauter et al. [24] analysed the feasibility of Somewhat Homomorphic Encryption (SHE) schemes along with an implementation by Brakerski and Vaikuntanathan [25].

In 2010 Van Dijk et al. [26] proposed a scheme based on integers, that was proposed as a simpler alternative to the already mentioned lattice-based ones. Later, researchers in [27], [28] focused on the scheme in order to achieve performance comparable to the one of the lattice-based schemes. The application of compression techniques in public keys reduced the size in about 10 MB from the initial 2 GB. Researchers in [12] introduced the encryption of multiple plaintext bits into one ciphertext through the usage of a batching technique and upgraded the performance of the aforementioned schemes. Their performance is similar to another implementation presented by Gentry et al. in [8], using the RLWE based FHE scheme.

A number of optimizations in the efficiency and speed have been emerged in the field of homomorphic encryption since the introduction of SHE and FHE [16]. Researches focused on improving or avoiding the bootstrapping process as it is quite expensive. Bootstrapping process aiming to minimise the noise in the ciphertext through the homomorphic decryption of a ciphertext, with the use of a secret key that is encrypted and masked into the public key. Brakerski et al. [29] proposed modulus switching which contributes in the noise reduction produced during homomorphic operations.

Implementations of FHE schemes are presented in [8] and [12] and additionally, an open-source one, HCRYPT, is already online [31]. Halevi and Shoup developed a library for homomorphic encryption, which implements an optimised FHE scheme based on Brakerski et al. proposal [29]. The implementation offered 8% increase in speed compared to the previous ones, in other words, it reduces the process time to 3 hours, in contrast with the initial 36 hours, for the homomorphic AES scheme [30], [31].

4.2.4. ACCEPT implementation

The homomorphic Encryption algorithm that is going to be implemented in order to remove the traceability of information origin, is based on the work presented in [32]. The paper presents a secure energy trading method based on blockchain technology and homomorphic encryption technology. This security mechanism is projected to be applied, in order to minimize the access to data subjects' personal information. Using homomorphic

encryption, elevates the data security, against confidentiality attacks, and at the same time it serves as an anonymization technique.

4.2.5. P2P Security Framework (QUE)

Blockchain Technology

This chapter describes the Peer-to-Peer (P2P) Blockchain security aspect, that will be implemented in the ACCEPT project for the design and the implementation of the P2P Exchange Platform. Blockchain, that lies at the center of the proposed solution, is a **secure** decentralized digital database that is based on the distributed ledger technology (DLT). The digital database is replicated in a network of distributed ledgers or computers in different locations. Any changes to the data must be updated concurrently so that all the ledgers always hold the same information. The decentralized structure and distributed ledger verification system enhance data security.

A predefined set of validators must evaluate and approve the information provided before adding it to the ledger. New information is only added after more than two-thirds of the validators approve it, as it is defined by the Byzantine Fault Tolerance (BFT) algorithms. BFT algorithms are the backbone of the DLT systems security, as they have the ability to identify and block threats, that could either originate from failing equipment or malicious behavior. Blockchain data is secured using layers of **intricate cryptography**. The data is considered **immutable** because all the ledgers in the system need to be edited simultaneously to successfully alter any entry. This makes it almost impossible to tamper with the data.

Each block on the chain has unique encryptions for the individual entry, the validator and the originator of the data. There can be extra encryption layers depending on the level of security desired. Blockchain technology prevents any central actor or authority from owning, controlling or manipulating the data.

Cosmos SDK Framework

The P2P Platform that will be designed, developed and used is based on the Cosmos Network project, a decentralized network of independent parallel blockchains, each powered by Tendermint Core, a BFT algorithm. The Tendermint Core ensures that the transactions are securely and reliably recorded on every machine in the same order, outperforming in speed and performance similar solutions.

The Cosmos Network is commonly referred to as the "Internet of Blockchains". It works much like the internet but connects blockchain systems instead of computer networks. Cosmos was designed to enhance blockchain interoperability and security. Before the introduction of Cosmos, blockchains were siloed and unable to communicate with each other. They were hard to build and could only handle a small number of transactions per second. Cosmos solves these problems by introducing a new technical vision. Using Cosmos SDK and Inter-Blockchain Communication (IBC) protocols, Cosmos facilitates the transfer of data and assets securely between blockchains regardless of specific programming language and architectural limitations.

Building a secure Blockchain app from scratch remains a difficult and non-secure task. Cosmos SDK facilitates and simplifies the process of building secure blockchain applications on top of Tendermint BFT, based on two major principles:

- **Modularity:** The goal of the Cosmos SDK is to create an ecosystem of modules that allows developers to easily spin up application-specific blockchains without having to code each bit of functionality of their application from scratch. Anyone can create a module for the Cosmos SDK, and using ready built modules in your blockchain is as simple as importing them into your application.
- **Capabilities-based security:** Capabilities constrain the security boundaries between modules, enabling developers to better reason about the composability of modules and limit the scope of malicious or unexpected interactions. It protects blockchains by limiting the interaction between modules that don't have pre-existing connectivity. This is necessary because anyone can develop the SDK modules and the network cannot prevent malicious developers from creating modules.

5. Conclusions

Deliverable is part Task T2.4-Security Access Control (SEAC) framework design & guidelines for technical solution developers of WP2 – Foundations of the ACCEPT project. In this document there is a presentation of all indications and restrictions imposed by the GDPR, that need to be taken into consideration, during the whole system design. Furthermore, there is a step-by-step analysis of the DPIA method, that will be followed by the pilots of the project, in order to assess security and privacy vulnerabilities. Finally, a description of the measures that are projected to be implemented to mitigate the threats present, along with the state-of-the-art analysis of the proposed technologies. The whole deliverable draws guidelines concerning the cybersecurity framework design that is going to be implemented. In Deliverable D2.6-Report on cybersecurity framework design & specifications for data protection & privacy v2, there will be a detailed technical analysis of all measures implemented, as well as all of the assessments conducted by the pilots, before and after the implementation of the threat mitigation measures.

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ANNEX I - Threats affecting Assets

Threat Category	Threat	Explanation of threat	Specific Energy industry examples of Supporting Asset vulnerabilities	Questions for guidance	Proposed mitigation strategies
Illegitimate processing of Personal Data	No lawfulness of processing	To process Personal Data it is necessary to have a legal basis defined in Art.6 GDPR or the national Data Protection laws (e.g. consent of the data subject, contract with the data subject, documented legitimate interest of the Data Controller, legal requirements)		Is there a documented legal basis defined for the lawfulness of Data Processing?	Defining a legal basis for the process and controlling if the process follows that legal basis
	Collection exceeding purpose	More Personal Data is collected than what is necessary to achieve a specified purpose.	Collecting more detailed load profile data for the purpose of monthly billing, where much less detailed data would be sufficient to achieve the same objective.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What Personal Data do you need to collect for the purpose? 2. Is the collected data proportional to the purpose? 	<p>Minimizing the amount of Personal Data.</p> <p>Active measure to preclude the use of particular data-items in the making of particular decisions</p> <p>Limits on the use of information for a very specific purpose, with strong legal, organisational and technical safeguards preventing its application for any other purpose</p>
	Unclear responsibilities for Data Processing.	It is not clear to data subjects what parties are involved in the processing of data and their respective roles.	Installation organisation is acting as a subcontractor for the metering operator and is collecting data for the grid operator. The energy service company (ESCo) hires a third party to collect data to provide energy saving	Are responsibilities clearly described and carried out for all parties? Is responsibility for Data Processing part of a sub-contractors contract?	Informing data subjects Make a privacy policy, code of conduct or certify the processing of the data to be more transparent

			advice to the consumer.		
	The protection of data is compromised outside the European Economic Area (EEA).	There is a risk that smart metering data may be at risk if sent outside of the EEA. Another risk is that Personal Data like metering data gives inside information about vital infrastructures in an unknown, maybe untruthful environment	Data Protection standards outside the EEA may not be secure and robust as those countries are not subject to the obligations within the GDPR. Foreign organisations use information about vital infrastructures and personal information to investigate people of interest.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Do you transfer the Personal Data outside the EEA? 2. To which country outside the EEA is the Personal Data transferred to? 3. Is the Personal Data transferred to a country that provides an adequate level of protection according to article 32 of GDPR? 4. How did you guarantee the protection of the Personal Data when transferred outside EEA? 5. Are all parties involved in implementation and operation established in the EU? 	<p>Anonymizing Personal Data Limiting Personal Data transfer to countries that provide an adequate level of protection according to the article 32 of the GDPR Active measures to preclude the disclosure of particular data-items Not transferring the source data, but only the outcomes</p>
Inadequate information of the data subject	Incomplete information	The information provided to the data subject on the purpose and use of data is not complete	Information provided to consumers only consists of usage data, information about other information (such as the ability to detect communication disruptions) gathered is not provided.	How did you notify the purpose of the processing operation of Personal Data to the consumers?	<p>Informing data subjects Clear and consistent communication of purpose and goals of data collection</p>
Violation of the data subject's rights	Inability to execute individual rights (inspection rights)	If data are going to be held by multiple Data Controllers, then consumers should have a means by which to access these data from multiple sources using a single	Petrol station and organisation providing invoices work together to enable charging of vehicles in joint controllership. Individuals should be provided with	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Is a procedure in place to easily inform consumers about the use of his Personal Data? 	<p>Informing data subjects Obtaining the consent of data subjects Giving the individual control over his or her data, for example by a secured website portal</p>

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		subject access request.	easy means to get insight in the data collected (e.g. by a unified user access right).		
	Prevention of objections	Data subjects have the right to object to the processing of data. If they want to execute this right it must be (technically) possible.	Consumers cannot opt out to reading of detailed energy load profiles because read-out schemes are not configurable: There are no technical or operational means to allow compliance with a data subject's objection.	1. Is it possible to change the collection of Personal Data in the Smart Grid Use Case after the consumer's objection? 2. Can consumers object to processing of Personal Data use by certain technologies?	Permitting the exercise of the right to object Make a privacy policy, code of conduct or certify the processing of the data to be more transparent
	A lack of transparency for automated individual decisions	Automated processing of Personal Data intended to evaluate certain personal aspects or conduct is used but the data subjects are not informed about the logic of the decision-making.	Remote disconnection is performed without providing clear explanation of the reasons to the user.	1. Are consumers informed of automated information processing? 2. How are the consumers notified of automated individual decisions?	Informing data subjects
	Lack of correction of Personal Data	There is no way for the data subject to initiate a correction of his data according to article 16 of the GDPR. The Data Controller and / or Data Processor are not sufficiently prepared to respond to such requests.	A personalized overview of Personal Data from the data subject cannot be corrected from the database that holds the data.	1. Are there processes to meet the consumer's rights on data collection, access, deletion and correction? 2. Are you able to provide overview of data collected? 3. Are you able to correct the data on request?	Permitting the exercise of the direct access right Allowing the exercise of the right to correct according to article 16 of the GDPR Design, implementation and resourcing of a responsive complaints-handling system, backed by serious sanctions and enforcement powers Give the individual control over his or her data, for example by a secured website portal
	Lack of erasure of Personal Data	There is no way for the data subject to initiate an	A personalized overview of Personal Data from the data	1. Are there processes to meet the	Permitting the exercise of the direct access right Allowing the exercise

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		erasure of his data according to article 17 of the GDPR. The Data Controller and / or Data Processor are not sufficiently prepared to respond to such requests.	subject cannot be erased from the database that holds the data.	consumer's rights on data collection, access, deletion and correction? 2. Are you able to provide overview of data collected? 3. Are you able to delete the data on request?	of the right to erase (right to be forgotten) according to article 17 of the GDPR Design, implementation and resourcing of a responsive complaints-handling system, backed by serious sanctions and enforcement powers Give the individual control over his data, for example by a secured website portal
Compliance violations in the contracts	Missing or incorrect contractual Data Protection clause	It is required to have a Data Protection clause in contracts for Data Processing on behalf. The content of the Data Protection clause is legally required and different in the EU countries. There are additional requirements for Data Processors in third Countries.	To provide consumption data to the customers by internet platforms IT-provider gets into contact with these data as a Data Processor.	Are there Data Protection clauses and technical and organizational measures defined in the contract with the provider involved in the process?	Implementation of Data Protection clauses for Data Processing on behalf together with the procurement department
Personal Data integrity loss	Lack of quality of data for the purpose of use	If data is used for certain processes, it should be adequate.	For billing on a daily basis data should be registered on a daily basis. For disconnecting electricity supply the exact location (address) and reasons should be conclusive. Based upon wrong consumption data a wrong invoice is sent. A comma is used as a separator where a full- stop is intended. This leads to wrong invoice.	1. Are automated input validation and reconciliation controls implemented? 2. How do you ensure data quality for the purpose of use? 3. Are there test procedures for data quality?	Monitoring the integrity of Personal Data Introduction of automated controls on the data quality
	Inability to	The data is	Metering data is	1. Are there	Allowing the exercise

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	respond to requests for subject access, correction or deletion of data in a timely and satisfying manner.	distributed across several business units and an integrated overview cannot be made within a short time frame.	stored and maintained by the technical department, reactions on commercial offers are stored at the commercial department, questions and answers are stored at the service department. Combining this data in one overview takes (a lot of) effort.	processes to meet the consumer's rights on data collection, access, deletion and correction? 2. Are you able to provide an overview of data collected? Are you able to provide what data is transferred to a third party? 3. Can an overview of what data is provided to whom be provided? 4. Are you able to delete the data on request?	of the right to correct Design, implementation and resourcing of a responsive complaints-handling system, backed by serious sanctions and enforcement powers Give the individual control over his or her data, for example by a secured website portal.
Damage to Individual	Discrimination				
	Identify Theft or Fraud				
	Financial loss				
	Other significant economic or social disadvantage				

ANNEX II - Severity & Likelihood Scale

Severity	Description	Level of Severity
Negligible	Identifying an individual using its Personal Data appears to be virtually impossible (e.g. searching throughout a Member State population on one meter reading). Data subjects either will not be affected or may encounter a few inconveniences, which they will overcome without any problem (time spent re-entering information, annoyances, irritations, etc.).	1
Limited	Identifying an individual using their Personal Data appears to be difficult but is possible in certain cases (e.g. searching throughout a Member State population using an individual's 1-day history of meter readings). Data subjects may encounter significant inconveniences, which they will be able to overcome despite a few difficulties (extra costs, denial of access to business services, fear, lack of understanding, stress, minor physical ailments, etc.).	2
Moderate	Identifying an individual using their Personal Data appears to be common (e.g. searching throughout a Member State population using an individual's 1-week history of meter readings). Data subjects may encounter consequences, which they will be able to overcome (extra costs due to denial of access to business services, delay, fury, minor physical ailments, etc.).	3
Significant	Identifying an individual using their Personal Data appears to be relatively easy (e.g. searching throughout a Member State population using an individual's history of meter readings of multiple days). Data subjects may encounter significant consequences, which they should be able to overcome albeit with serious difficulties (misappropriation of funds, blacklisting by banks, property damage, loss of employment, subpoena, worsening of state of health, etc.).	4
Maximum	Identifying an individual using their Personal Data appears to be extremely easy (e.g. searching throughout a Member State population using an individual's history of meter readings). Data subjects may encounter significant, or even irreversible, consequences, which they may not overcome (financial distress such as substantial debt or inability to work, long-term psychological or physical ailments, death, etc.).	5

Likelihood	Description	Level of Likelihood
Negligible	Carrying out a Threat by exploiting the Vulnerabilities of Supporting Assets does not appear possible (e.g. theft of paper documents stored in a room protected by a badge reader and access code). Risk sources do not appear to have any special capabilities to carry out a Threat (e.g. software function creep by an individual acting without malicious intent and who has limited access privileges).	1
Limited	Carrying out a Threat by exploiting the Vulnerabilities of Supporting Assets appears to be difficult (e.g. theft of paper documents stored in a room protected by a badge reader). The capabilities of Risks Sources to carry out a Threat are limited (e.g.: software function creep by a malicious individual with limited access privileges).	2
Moderate	Carrying out a Threat by exploiting the Vulnerabilities of Supporting Assets appears to be common (e.g. theft of paper documents stored in a room protected by a master key). The capabilities of Risk Sources to carry out a Threat are common (e.g. software function creep by a malicious individual with limited administration privileges).	3
Significant	Carrying out a Threat by exploiting the Vulnerabilities of Supporting Assets appears to be possible (e.g. theft of paper documents stored in offices that cannot be accessed without first checking in at reception). The capabilities of Risk Sources to carry out a Threat are real and significant (e.g. software function creep by an individual acting without malicious intent and who has unlimited administration privileges).	4
Maximum	Carrying out a Threat by exploiting the Vulnerabilities of Supporting Assets appears to be extremely easy (e.g. theft of paper documents stored in a lobby). The capabilities of Risk Sources to carry out a threat are defined and unlimited (e.g. software function creep by a malicious individual with unlimited administration privileges).	5

ANNEX III - List of possible controls

No	Name of a Control	Control's Objective
1.	Managing contracts between Data Controllers and Data Processors	to reduce the risks associated with missing or incorrect contractual Data Protection clauses
2.	Managing third parties with legitimate access to Personal Data	to reduce the risk that legitimate access to Personal Data by third parties may pose to the data subjects' rights and freedoms.
3.	Monitoring logical access controls	to limit the risks that unauthorized persons will access Personal Data electronically.
4.	Partitioning Personal Data	to reduce the possibility that Personal Data can be correlated and that a breach of all Personal Data may occur.
5.	Encrypting Personal Data	to make Personal Data unintelligible to anyone without access authorization.
6.	Anonymizing Personal Data	to remove identifying characteristics from Personal Data.
7.	Protecting Personal Data archives	to define all procedures for preserving and managing the electronic archives containing the Personal Data.
8.	Managing Personal Data violations	to have an operational organisation that can detect and treat incidents that may affect the data subjects' civil liberties and privacy.
9.	Tracing the activity on the IT system	to allow early detection of incidents involving Personal Data and to have information that can be used to analyse them or provide proof in connection with investigations.
10.	Combating malicious codes	to protect access to public (Internet) and uncontrolled (partner) networks, workstations and servers from malicious codes that could affect the security of Personal Data.
11.	Reducing software vulnerabilities	to reduce the possibility to exploit software properties (operating systems, business applications, database management systems, office suites, protocols, configurations, etc.) to adversely affect Personal Data.
12.	Reducing hardware vulnerabilities	to reduce the possibility to exploit hardware properties (servers, desktop computers, laptops, devices, communications relays, removable storage devices, etc.) to adversely affect Personal Data.
13.	Reducing the vulnerabilities of computer communications networks	to reduce the possibility to exploit communications networks properties (wired networks, Wi-Fi, radio waves, fibre optics, etc.) to adversely affect Personal Data.
14.	Reducing the vulnerabilities of paper documents	to reduce the possibility to exploit paper documents properties to adversely affect Personal Data.
15.	Reducing vulnerabilities related to the circulation of paper documents	to reduce the possibility to exploit paper document circulation properties (within an organisation, delivery by vehicle, mail delivery, etc.) to adversely affect Personal Data.
16.	Create procedures to address CoT and	To ensure that after such a change, no Personal Data is available

	CoS	
17.	Permitting the exercise of the right to object	to ensure that individuals have an opportunity to object to the use of their Personal Data.
18.	Monitoring the integrity of Personal Data	to be warned in the event of an unwanted modification or disappearance of Personal Data.
19.	Reducing the vulnerabilities of individuals	to reduce the possibility to exploit people (employees, individuals who are not part of an organisation but are under its responsibility, etc.) by adversely affecting Personal Data.
20.	No collection of identifiable information, only pseudonyms, or anonym data	to prevent identification of the data subject through collected data.
21.	Active measure to preclude the use of particular data-items in the making of particular decisions	to ensure that decisions are made based only on due data-items.
22.	Limits on the use of information for a very specific purpose, with strong legal, organisational and technical safeguards preventing its application to any other purpose	to ensure that information is used for the specified purpose and for nothing more than that.
23.	Active measures to preclude the disclosure of particular data-items	to ensure that only required and permitted data-items are disclosed.
24.	Minimisation of Personal Data retention by destroying it as soon as the transaction for which it is needed is completed	to ensure compliance with legislation and to prevent misuse of Personal Data.
25.	Destruction schedules for personal information	to ensure compliance with legislation and to prevent misuse of Personal Data.
26.	Use of mathematical methods without collecting and registration source data to reach goals	to avoid collection of non-authorized data without prejudice to reach goals.
27.	Give the individual control over his or her data, for example by a secured website portal	to ensure that the individual has control over his or her data according to his rights and responsibilities.
28.	Introduction automated controls on the data quality	to ensure that data quality is monitored and maintained on a regular basis.
29.	Design, implementation and resourcing of a responsive complaints-handling system, backed by serious sanctions and enforcement powers	to ensure that clients have a way of communicating their requests and complaints and to ensure that these are timely and adequately addressed.
30.	Audit	a generic control to ensure that all implemented Controls are in place
31.	Informing data subjects Clear and consistent communication of purpose and goals of data collection	
32.	Obtaining the consent of data subjects	
33.	Permitting the exercise of the direct access right	
34.	Allowing the exercise of the right to correct according to article 16 of the GDPR	
35.	Allowing the exercise of the right to	

erase (right to be forgotten) according to article 17 of the GDPR	
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